

DEVELOPMENT OF A 3D FINITE ELEMENT MODEL OF A QUASI-STATIC INDENTATION TEST IN A TYPE III CYLINDER

Erick Montes de Oca Valle¹, Ian Sinclair¹, Mark Spearing¹, Trevor Allen¹ and Warren Hepples²

¹University of Southampton, University Road, Southampton, SO17 1BJ, UK

²Luxfer Gas Cylinders, 56 Road, Colwick, Nottingham, NG4 2BH, UK

E-mail: emdo1g15@soton.ac.uk

ABSTRACT

This paper describes an early stage work that belongs to a project which investigates the mechanical and structural properties of Type III cylinders. In this work, a 3D finite element model of a quasi-static indentation test was developed. The main feature of the model is the cohesive zone developed to describe the interface between the aluminium liner and the composite layers of the cylinder. As well as predicting the metal-composite de-cohesion under the indentation area, the model can predict the residual indentation depth based on the parameters explored for the cohesive zone. Results are discussed in relation to experimental data previously obtained. Limitations and improvements associated with different modelling parameters (e.g. boundary conditions and mesh dependency) are discussed and considered for the future stages of the project.

1. INTRODUCTION

This project investigates the structural behaviour of composite pressure vessels under quasi-static indentation loading, which has been shown to be a useful proxy for impact. According to global market analysts[1] the production demand for composite pressure vessels will continue to increase at a growth rate of 8.5% through 2020. This growth is driven by the increase in the development of the alternative fuels market, including hydrogen and natural gas-powered vehicles[2]. Therefore, effort is required to develop manufacturing and design processes for composite pressure vessels in order to provide cost effective solutions while meeting vehicle safety regulations. This requires investigation of their mechanical and structural performance under specific design conditions. Damage tolerance under impact loading is of particular concern.

Composite pressure vessels are cylindrical containers designed to hold gases at high pressures (up to 700 Bar). They are available in different types: *Type I*, pure metal pressure vessel; *Type II*, metal cylinders with a composite wrapped hoop section; *Type III*, made of an aluminium liner fully wrapped in composite filaments and *Type IV*, made of a plastic liner fully wrapped in composite filaments[2]. There have been several studies regarding stress distribution and damage development within type III cylinders subjected to pressure and impact loads. For instance, Son et al.[3] proposed different techniques to model type III cylinders under pressure load and validate them through experimental tests. Subsequently, Son used this technique to develop a model of a Type III cylinder under free fall condition[4], in which 3D elements,

residual stresses resulting from *autofrettage* manufacturing process and friction between the liner and the composite layers were included. Son's model was used to evaluate the structural state of a cylinder after an impact based only on the "failure index" of the outermost layer. Despite good correlation with experimental tests, the study does not include information regarding the influence of the damage on the fatigue life of the cylinder. Marzbanrad et al.[5] performed a similar study in which they evaluated the influence of the fibre angle orientation on the stress distribution and applied it to evaluate fatigue life. Their model lacks detail regarding liner damage, matrix failure and delamination areas.

The above studies focused on predicting damage modes such as delamination and matrix failure caused by pressure application or a low-velocity impact event. However, other damage mechanisms have been observed in type III cylinders which have not been studied deeply. Previous research based on experimental tests, concluded that a type III cylinder subjected to a quasi-static indentation test (a good proxy for a low-velocity impact) will develop a *blister* like failure, that is, a separation between the liner and the carbon fibre layers[6]. Moreover, it was shown that there is a direct correlation between the depth of the blister and the fatigue life of the cylinder, i.e. the deeper the blister the more the reduction on the fatigue cycle life. The relation between the existence of the blister and the fatigue life performance reduction can be understood with the concepts of damage resistance and damage tolerance. If type III cylinders' damage tolerance can be properly assessed, better design approaches can be developed in order to ensure the integrity of the component throughout its service life. Hence, analysis of the blister formation mechanism (occurring at the aluminium-composite interface) is required.

In summary, this project aims to develop a 3D finite element model to predict the blister formation and separation between the aluminium liner and the composite layers of a type III cylinder. For this model, it is assumed that, as a result of the autofrettage process, there is a bonding between the liner and the composite material whereas in previous research no bonding was considered[4]. Consequently, de-cohesion progression is to be investigated in this model via the definition of the mechanical properties of the interface by applying cohesive zone modelling (CZM). Results were compared to data previously obtained in experimental tests[6] to validate the model. It is important to note that the results presented in this paper explore the macroscale structural behaviour of the de-cohesion mechanism as an early research stage of the project. Furthermore, physical testing should be performed to validate the virtual model at different levels (e.g. meso and microstructural levels). It is expected that a better understanding of this interface may result in new manufacturing approaches to diminish the blister formation after a low-velocity impact and, thus, enhance the fatigue life performance of the cylinder.

2. EXPERIMENTATION

One of the main challenges of this project is the understanding of the mechanical properties which drive the progression of de-cohesion between the liner and the composite layers in a type III cylinder. Based on these needs, finite element analysis and cohesive zone modelling were explored to develop the model. AbaqusTM software was chosen due to its built-in capabilities for composites and cohesive zone modelling.

2.1 Model description

The model replicates the quasi-static indentation procedure developed in previous research in which the blister was observed[6]. The indentation was performed in the cylindrical region of the cylinder with an 8 mm spherical indenter. The investigation of the model was developed based in one type III cylinder size. The simulation was carried out within 2 steps; a loading

step to create the indentation and an unloading step to observe the residual deformation. Table 2-1 shows the geometrical characteristics of the cylinder.

Table 2-1. Type A cylinder dimensions

Reference name	Water Volume [l]	Length [mm]	Outside Diameter [mm]	Liner Thickness [mm]	Carbon Fiber Thickness [mm]
Type A	1.0	295	85	1.8	2.0

In order to save computational time, 1/4th of the cylinder was modelled using appropriate symmetric boundary conditions. The dome region of the cylinder is known to be complex as the filaments directions constantly vary through the surface as well as the thickness[3]. Moreover, the indentation is considered far from this region, thus, the dome geometry was not modelled to avoid the complexity involved. An end plate was included in the model, with a bending stiffness matched to that of the dome, instead to provide appropriate boundary conditions.

The aluminium used for the liner was a 6061-T6 with the elastic and plastic behaviour of this material. The composite material is a carbon fibre reinforced epoxy with stacking sequence of $[\pm 55_2/0_4]_3$. Mechanical properties of the materials are described in Table 2-2.

Table 2-2. Material properties

Name	Young's Modulus [GPa]	Yield Strength [MPa]	Poisson's Ratio	Shear Modulus [GPa]
Aluminum	69	270	0.33	-
CFRP	$E_1 = 161.74$ $E_2 = E_3 = 161.74$	-	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.33$ $\nu_{23} = 0.43$	$G_{12} = G_{13} = 4.57$ $G_{23} = 3.1$

2.2 Cohesive Zone Modelling (CZM)

Cohesive zone modelling allows the characterization of crack propagation including non-linearity of the fracture behaviour of the material. This approach considers that the inelastic effects occurring in the vicinity of a crack can be merged into a single surface called the cohesive damage zone[7], [8]. The CZM characterizes the cohesive force-displacement relationship acting within a non-linear deformation damage region.

Cohesive zones are governed by a traction-separation law, which can be interpreted physically as defining a critical maximum stress and total energy for fracture (the area under the force-displacement curve) which is equal to the total critical strain energy release rate. A typical constitutive response for a traction-separation law is divided in damage initiation and damage evolution. The former occurs when the traction reaches a value at which damage starts and the latter describes the rate at which the stiffness of the cohesive zone is degraded[9]. Figure 2-1 shows a bilinear traction-separation law where T_{max} is the maximum traction, δ_{sep} is the displacement at separation and G_c is the critical energy release rate, which is the total energy dissipated as a result of the damage process[10].

Figure 2-1. Bilinear traction-separation law

Within Abaqus™ it is possible to implement this traction separation law by defining the parameters mentioned above. However, Abaqus™ adds the parameter K_n as a penalty stiffness parameter due to the lack of certain information such as the effective elastic modulus of the interface[9]. Furthermore, the implementation of the cohesive zone in this project is via cohesive elements, which allow it to have a better control on damage initiation and evolution parameters. Each different parameter defining the cohesive element has been investigated with regards to their influence on the results.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Mesh dependency

The first parameter to validate the reliability of the simulation is the influence of the mesh size on the results. The mesh is constituted of 3D bricks except for the rigid parts where the mesh was created as a shell (indenter and support). Here, the same model was solved with different average mesh size (MS): 2.0 mm, 1.0 mm and 0.5 mm. Figure 3-1 shows a comparison of four different force-displacement curves, i.e. the experimental curve and the model with three different mesh sizes. Although the three curves adjust well to the initial stiffness, it is clear that the mesh size of 2.0 mm is not adequate for this model. On the other hand, both 1.0 and 0.5 offer a good correlation with the experimental data. However, the 0.5 mesh takes almost twice the time to converge to the final solution, thus, the 1.0 mm mesh size was considered acceptable.

Figure 3-1. Mesh dependency test

3.2 Cohesive zone investigation results

The type III cylinder model was used to explore the cohesive elements influence of the cohesive response on the force-displacement curves. The experimental data exhibits a quasi-bilinear response in which a high initial stiffness is observed followed by a change in the slope of the curve. Towards the end of the loading stage, a small load drop can be observed. It was concluded[6] that this load drop is related to delamination and matrix crack damage mechanisms. The influence of three features on the resultant stiffness was analysed: the addition of the end plate as a boundary condition; the cohesive response in the different failure modes and the cohesive penalty stiffness K_n .

As mentioned previously, as this is an early staged project, the modelling complexity related to the dome region was not included in this model. That is why, an end plate was added instead to compensate for the initial stiffness. Figure 3-2 shows the comparison of the same model with and without the metal plate at the end. It can be observed that although both curves are reasonably close to the experimental loading curve the model with the end plate compares better to the initial stiffness response.

The CZM traction values in modes II and III were modified to investigate their influence on the shape of the force-displacement curves. Within the development of the model it was observed that the main propagation of de-cohesion occurs during the loading phase and is mainly driven by modes II and III rather than mode I. Figure 3-3 describes the comparison of the results obtained at different traction values. None of the traction laws showed significant influence on the initial stiffness of the overall cylinder; however, it does influence the final reaction force value and the unloading curve. Considering those outputs, the value of 50 GPa for modes II and III show better agreement to the experimental curve.

Figure 3-2. Type A cylinder model with and without plate as boundary condition

Figure 3-3. Force-displacement curves at different traction values (modes II and III)

Finally, the value of K_n was modified and results were registered. Figure 3-4 shows the resultant force-displacement curves with 1, 3 and 5 $\left[\frac{kN}{mm^3}\right]$. Although there is some change in with $K_n = 1$, values of 3 and 5 did not contribute to a significant difference with respect to the overall initial stiffness. However, as this value governs the stiffness of the interface the main influence was observed on the delamination area under the indentation, which will be used in future stages based on bigger sized cylinders.

Figure 3-4. Force-displacement curves at different penalty stiffness values

4. CONCLUSIONS

4.1 Modelling outcomes

The current work is an early stage study of a bigger project which investigates damage tolerance in composite pressure vessels to develop safer and better designs. A 3D finite element model which predicts the de-cohesion damage mode of a type III cylinder under a quasi-static indentation test has been developed. The interface between the aluminium liner and the composite layers was modelled using cohesive elements. Force-displacement curves were obtained and compared to experimental data. Although this early model will be further enhanced, the results presented in this paper allow the definition the aluminium-carbon interface parameters.

From the values analysed, the conclusions are the following:

- For the quasi-static loading, adding an end plate to match the stiffness to that of the dome region is acceptable to replicate the initial stiffness response, as the load occurs sufficiently far from this region.
- Modifying the CZM values of modes II and III have representative influence on the force-displacement response. On the contrary, modifying the stiffness of the cohesive zone does not influences the overall force-displacement response.

4.2 Future work

As mentioned before, the current model is an early stage work and there are opportunity areas to be explored. For instance:

- The residual stresses arisen from the autofrettage process should be added to explore the influence over the model behaviour.
- Up to now, the cylindrical region of the pressure vessel has been loaded. However, future investigation will require the dome region to be modelled.
- The model and the previous experimental results were performed on empty cylinders. Nevertheless, pressurized conditions should be explored as well.
- Experimental tests to get mechanical properties in the actual specimen (such as the energy release rate) will be conducted and compared to the FE results.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] Reportlinker, “Growth Opportunities in the Global Composite Cylinder Market 2015-2020: Trends, Forecast, and Opportunity Analysis, October 2015,” 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/growth-opportunities-in-the-global-composite-cylinder-market-2015-2020-trends-forecast-and-opportunity-analysis-october-2015-300197054.html>.
- [2] M. LEGAULT, “Pressure vessel tank types,” 2012. [Online]. Available: <http://www.compositesworld.com/articles/pressure-vessel-tank-types>.
- [3] M.-G. G. Han *et al.*, “Evaluation of modeling techniques for a type III hydrogen pressure vessel (70 MPa) made of an aluminum liner and a thick carbon/epoxy composite for fuel cell vehicles,” *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 37, no. 11, pp. 12771–12781, 2012.
- [4] M. G. Han and S. H. Chang, “Evaluation of structural integrity of Type-III hydrogen pressure vessel under low-velocity car-to-car collision using finite element analysis,” *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 148, pp. 198–206, 2016.
- [5] J. Marzbanrad, A. Paykani, A. Afkar, and M. Ghajar, “Finite element analysis of composite high-pressure hydrogen storage vessels,” *Environ. Sci*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 63–74, 2013.
- [6] T. M. Allen, “Damage Development and Post-Impact Performance of Composite Overwrapped Pressure Vessels Subjected to Low Velocity Impact,” University of Southampton, 2017.
- [7] S. Iqbar Wakar, “An Evaluation of Zone Cohesive Models for Adhesives Failure in Bonded Joints,” University of Southampton, 2011.
- [8] A. Turon, P. P. Camanho, J. Costa, and J. Renart, “Accurate simulation of delamination growth under mixed-mode loading using cohesive elements: Definition of interlaminar strengths and elastic stiffness,” *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 92, no. 8, pp. 1857–1864, 2010.
- [9] Dassault Systemes, “32.5.6 Defining the constitutive response of cohesive elements using a traction-separation description,” 2014.
- [10] D. Soteropoulos, K. a. Fetfatsidis, and J. a. Sherwood, “Using Abaqus to Model Delamination in Fiber-Reinforced Composite Materials,” *Simulia.Com*, pp. 1–13, 2012.